

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Nurses' knowledge about the implementation of medical tourism in Hospitals

Ida Bagus Maha Gandamayu *, Ni Wayan Sukma Antari, Luh Gde Nita Sri Wahyuningsih and I Ketut Alit Adianta

Bali Institute of Technology and Health, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(01), 1475-1479

Publication history: Received on 29 November 2024; revised on 06 January 2025; accepted on 08 January 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0064>

Abstract

Medical tourism can be defined as a trip made by a person abroad for the purpose of obtaining health care, either in the form of general check-ups, medical treatment, or medical rehabilitation (Alwi et al., 2022). Knowledge of health workers in this case, especially nurses related to medical tourism is very important as one of the initial capital in the successful implementation of medical tourism activities in Bali. This study is to determine the knowledge of nurses as health professionals in supporting medical tourism services at hospitals in Bali. The design of this study is descriptive cross sectional. The population in this study were nurses who worked at Bali Mandara Regional General Hospital, Mangusada Badung Regional General Hospital and Siloam Bali Hospital within 4 months (June-September 2023). The sampling technique in this study was accidental sampling. The number of respondents in this study was 80 people. Data collection using a questionnaire prepared by the researcher. The data that has been collected is analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS for Windows, Release 23.0). The data analyzed included descriptive analysis (mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage and range). The majority of respondents in this study showed an average age of 30 years, 65 people (81.3%) were female and had a Bachelor of Nursing Education background of 57 people (71.3%). Most of the respondents 58 (72.5%) had good knowledge and only 22 (27.5%) had sufficient knowledge about the implementation of medical tourism in hospitals. It is hoped that in the future health workers and hospitals are ready to implement medical tourism services.

Keywords: Medical Tourism; Knowledge; Nurse; Medical; Tourism

1. Introduction

The scope of tourism includes various activities and interesting facilities provided by a tourist attraction for tourists to spend their holidays (Rosalina, Suteja, Putra, & Pitanatri, 2015). Tourism activities have now been recognized not only as a product that can satisfy tourists, but also as a business opportunity that can then become a driver of the rate of economic activity of a tourist destination (UNWTO, 2008). The term Health Tourism in its services is divided into two parts, namely Medical Tourism and Wellness Tourism (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2014). Health development in Indonesia aims to achieve a healthy standard of living for all people so that they can improve their health optimally. To assess the success of a health development program, one approach that can be used is to see which factors are more focused on when organizing health services. In the curative paradigm, the focus is more on steps to treat emerging disease disorders, while the preventive paradigm focuses more on what steps can be taken to avoid the emergence of a disease (Rosalina et al., 2015).

Medical tourism can be interpreted as a trip taken by someone abroad for the purpose of obtaining health care, either in the form of a general check-up, medical care, or medical rehabilitation (Alwi et al., 2022). Common actions taken in medical tourism activities are dental care, surgery, cosmetic surgery, fertility treatment, organ transplantation, cancer treatment and others (Lunt et al., 2014). As we all know, many Indonesian citizens prefer to seek treatment abroad, one

* Corresponding author: Ida Bagus Maha Gandamayu

of the reasons is that the health industry in Indonesia is still less competitive than abroad. This fact certainly causes Indonesia's income in the health and tourism sectors to decrease. If we look at the developments that have occurred in the ASIA region, it is estimated that countries in the Asian region receive more than 1.3 million medical tourists each year. Patients who are customers of health services are the controllers of the health sector performance produced by a health service. This is because these patients also bring their families and friends to health care facilities. Patients who do not have quick access to health services due to various obstacles such as limited insurance policies, long waiting times, and unavailable treatment options will be the reason for them to travel abroad to choose the desired treatment (Ratnasari, Gunawan, Pitchay, & Mohd Salleh, 2022).

Seeing the development of the medical tourism trend that continues to increase in Asian countries, it is a golden opportunity for Bali and a promising potential to be developed in the future. By seeing the success of medical tourism in Asian countries, it certainly gives hope and opportunities for Bali to develop into a medical tourism destination of choice for tourists. Of course, by making several improvements in various sectors such as infrastructure, facilities, health workers, regulations, and other supporting factors. And planned comprehensively so that the concept of developing medical tourism can be realized. Since 2012, the Indonesian Ministry of Health has had a plan and prepared Indonesia as a medical tourism destination. Various physical preparations have been made, Indonesia itself already has 19 hospitals accredited internationally by the Joint Commission International with a total of 891,897 health workers in 2014. Bali as one of the prima donna destinations in Indonesia, has also tried to prepare international standard hospitals to support the implementation of medical tourism services (Rosalina et al., 2015). Nursing as a professional and comprehensive service must act based on science.

The knowledge of health workers in this case, especially nurses, regarding medical tourism is very important as one of the initial capitals in making the implementation of medical tourism activities in Bali a success. A deeper understanding of medical tourism such as service standards, types of medical services provided, advantages and benefits of medical tourism activities and basic skills that nurses must have been things that should be understood before being involved in medical tourism services. This study will be conducted at private hospitals in the Denpasar and Badung areas to see the extent to which nurses are prepared as professional health workers in supporting hospitals in Bali, especially the Denpasar and Badung areas, in preparing themselves to provide medical tourism services.

2. Methods

The design of this study is descriptive cross-sectional. The location of this study is Bali Mandara Regional General Hospital, Mangusada Badung Regional General Hospital and Siloam Bali Hospital. The population in this study were nurses working in each of these hospitals. The sampling technique used in this study was accidental sampling. The sample in this study will be selected based on the criteria determined by the author during the data collection period. The inclusion criteria in this study are nurses who are willing to be respondents and are not on leave and the exclusion criteria are nurses who are on study assignments. The data in this study will be analyzed using the SPSS for Windows version 22.0.

The variables measured or observed in this study are knowledge about medical tourism such as the definition or understanding of terms, service standards, types of services, advantages and benefits and basic skills that nurses must have. Determination of the choice of analysis will be determined after seeing the distribution of data distribution. Research permits are processed at the Investment and Licensing Board of the Bali Provincial Government.

The ethical principles in this study include implementing the principle of autonomy through providing informed consent to prospective respondents and signing as approval. Participants will receive an explanation of the purpose, procedures, rights, potential benefits and time required to complete the questionnaire. All information related to the results of the study will be kept confidential. Physical and psychological comfort will be provided to participants in this study. They will be informed that their participation is also allowed to be withdrawn at any time if they feel uncomfortable without any penalty or compensation. The expected results of this study are to provide an overview of nurses' knowledge about medical tourism activities as an initial step to prepare hospitals in Indonesia, especially Bali, in providing medical tourism services.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Respondent Characteristics (n=80)

Variable	Frequency (n)/ Mean	Percentage (%)/±SD
Age	30.39	7.36
Gender		
Male	15	18.8
Female	65	81.3
Educational Background (Nursing)		
Diploma's degree	21	26.3
Bachelor's degree	57	71.3
Master's degree	2	2.5
Income		
500.000-2.500.000	23	28.7
>2.500.000-5.000.000	51	63.8
>5.000.000	6	7.5

Primary Data, 2024

Table 1 shows the average age of respondents in this study was 30.39 years (7.36). Most respondents in this study were male, 65 people (81.3%) with a bachelor's degree in nursing, 57 people (71.3%). Most of the respondents' income in this study was in the range of >2,500,000 - 5,000,000, namely 51 (63.8%).

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Statements of Knowledge of Medical Tourism Implementation (n = 80)

Variable	True	False
	F (%)	F (%)
Medical Tourism is a trip to another country to get medical treatment	78 (97.5)	2 (2.5)
Patients who do Medical Tourism are called Medical Tourists	78 (97.5)	2 (2.5)
Medical Tourists obtain information and book medical services through websites	80 (100)	-
Medical Tourism is only available at Hospitals abroad	58 (72.5)	22 (27.5)
Additional benefits of Medical Tourism can enjoy travel and tourist facilities	73 (91.3)	7 (8.8)
Health workers in Medical Tourism services are fluent in foreign languages	79 (98.8)	1 (1.3)
Requirements for Hospitals providing Medical Tourism are internationally accredited	72 (90.0)	8 (10.0)
Medical Tourism specifically handles chronic health problems only	68 (85.0)	12 (15.0)
Medical Tourism requires support from health workers, tourism actors, the community and the government	80 (100)	-
Medical Tourism services prioritize friendly and professional attitudes from health workers	80 (100)	-
Medical Tourism is only for the middle to upper economic class	51 (63.7)	29 (36.3)
Medical Tourism activities can only be carried out in private hospitals	53 (66.3)	27 (33.8)
Indonesia is a country that has the potential to develop Medical Tourism	79 (98.9)	1 (1.3)
The purpose of Medical Tourism is to get treatment, check-ups or medication	75 (93.8)	5 (6.3)
Medical Tourism only involves foreign health workers	65 (81.3)	15 (18.8)

Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 2, the total statements given to 80 respondents were 15 statements consisting of 10 positive statements and 5 negative statements. Of the 80 respondents, most respondents answered the category "True" in statements 9 and 10, while the most of respondents answered the category "False" in negative statements number 11 and 12.

Table 3 Distribution of Nurses' Knowledge Categories Regarding the Implementation of Medical Tourism (n = 80)

Knowledge	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Good	58	72.5
Average	22	27.5

Primary Data, 2024

Table 3 shows that the knowledge of nurses who were respondents in this study regarding the implementation of Medical Tourism shows good knowledge. Where most respondents have good knowledge 58 (72.5%) and only 22 (27.5%) have sufficient knowledge about medical tourism (Table 3).

The study's results show that the majority of respondents in this study showed an average age of 30 years, were female, 65 people (81.3%), and had a Bachelor's degree in Nursing, 57 people (71.3%). Most respondents have Good knowledge about the implementation of medical tourism in hospitals. This can be seen from the distribution of the knowledge level category results carried out; 58 (72.5%) have Good knowledge, and only 22 (27.5%) have Sufficient knowledge about implementing medical tourism in hospitals. Based on Table 2, distribution of questionnaire statements, of the 15 statements given to 80 respondents, the majority could answer Correctly on most statement items.

Education is one of the factors that influences knowledge. A nurse's knowledge is influenced by the education they have. This is related to the development of nursing science. The depth and extent of the knowledge possessed will affect the nurse's ability to think critically in carrying out nursing actions (Eriawan & Ardiana, 2013). Based on the distribution of respondent characteristics in this study, the majority of nurse respondents have a Bachelor's degree (S1 Nursing) so that the knowledge of the majority of nurses is in the Good category.

This study's results align with research conducted by (Wijaya & Goenarso, 2016) regarding the level of nurses' knowledge of patient safety in hospitals. Most nurses in the study had knowledge of the Good criteria. Nursing as a professional service must act based on knowledge. Quality and competent nursing services will be realized if nurses have a Bachelor's degree or more. To provide excellent service to tourists, especially foreign tourists, available health facilities such as clinics or hospitals should be able to deliver quality services according to international standards, especially when dealing with health problems experienced by tourists. All elements of medical staff such as nurses, doctors, midwives and paramedics are expected to have adequate knowledge and service standards (Wirawan et al., 2021).

The results of this study are expected to provide an overview of health workers' knowledge, especially nurses, in supporting medical tourism services in Bali. In addition, this study is expected to be an initial reference for health workers and health service institutions to prepare themselves to provide medical tourism services in Bali. Future research can examine the readiness of health workers and hospitals to carry out medical tourism services.

4. Conclusion

The study demonstrates that the majority of respondents, with an average age of 30 years, were female and held a Bachelor's degree in Nursing. A significant proportion of the respondents (72.5%) exhibited Good knowledge about the implementation of medical tourism in hospitals. Education emerged as a crucial factor influencing nurses' knowledge, aligning with prior research that links advanced education to better competency and critical thinking abilities in nursing. The findings suggest that the quality of nursing services is significantly enhanced when nurses possess a Bachelor's degree or higher, equipping them to provide services that meet international standards. This capability is essential for addressing health concerns of tourists, particularly foreign tourists, as part of medical tourism services in Bali. The study serves as a foundational reference for enhancing the readiness of health workers and health institutions in providing medical tourism services, emphasizing the importance of maintaining and improving knowledge and service standards.

4.1. Managerial Implications

To support the development of medical tourism services in Bali, health institutions should prioritize continuous professional development programs to enhance the knowledge and skills of nurses and other medical staff, focusing on cultural sensitivity, language proficiency, and international health standards. Hospitals and clinics must aim for international accreditation, ensuring alignment with global service benchmarks while upgrading facilities and adopting best practices. Recruitment strategies should emphasize hiring nurses with at least a Bachelor's degree, coupled with incentives and opportunities for advanced education. Additionally, collaboration with tourism agencies, hotels, and transport services can create integrated medical tourism packages, effectively promoted through strategic marketing campaigns highlighting Bali's healthcare excellence. Regular assessments of health worker readiness and facility preparedness are essential to continuously improve service delivery and maintain competitiveness in the medical tourism sector.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Alwi, N. P., Trianasari, N., Badi'ah, A., Haratikka, H., Rusli, M., Sejati, A. A., . . . Wuntu, G. (2022). Inovasi Medical Tourism: Media Sains Indonesia.
- [2] Eriawan, R. D., & Ardiana, A. (2013). Hubungan Tingkat Pengetahuan Perawat dengan Tindakan Keperawatan pada Pasien Pasca Operasi dengan General Aenesthesia di Ruang Pemulihan IBS RSD dr. Soebandi Jember. *Pustaka Kesehatan*, 1(1), 54-61.
- [3] Lunt, N., Smith, R. D., Mannion, R., Green, S. T., Exworthy, M., Hanefeld, J., . . . King, H. (2014). Implications for the NHS of inward and outward medical tourism: a policy and economic analysis using literature review and mixed-methods approaches.
- [4] Ratnasari, R. T., Gunawan, S., Pitchay, A. A., & Mohd Salleh, M. C. (2022). Sustainable medical tourism: Investigating health-care travel in Indonesia and Malaysia. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 15(3), 220-229.
- [5] Rosalina, P. D., Suteja, I. W., Putra, G. B. B., & Pitanatri, P. D. S. (2015). Membuka pintu pengembangan medical tourism di Bali. *JUMPA*, 1(2), 134-149.
- [6] Wijaya, H., & Goenarso, R. A. (2016). Tingkat pengetahuan perawat tentang Patient Safety di rumah sakit Adi Husada Surabaya. *Adi Husada Nursing Journal*, 2(1), 68-74.
- [7] Wirawan, I. M. A., Putri, W. C. W. S., Mulyawan, K. H., Kom, S., Kurniasari, N. M. D., SKM, M., . . . Suharlim, C. (2021). *Kesehatan dan Keselamatan Wisata: Direktori Hazard, Risiko, dan Layanan Kesehatan Wisata di Bali*: Penerbit Andi.
- [8] Kementerian Kesehatan RI, 2014. Menyambut Babak Baru Health Tourism di Indonesia. (<https://kesmas.kemkes.go.id/konten/133/0/081323-menyambut-babak-baru-health-tourism-di-indonesia>)
- [9] UNWTO-UNEP-WMO (2008) *Climate change and tourism: Responding to global challenges*. Madrid: UNWTO (<https://www.unwto.org/glossary-tourism-terms>).